

Thiopegan Derivatives. Part XXV. Synthesis of 9,10-Thiopegan Derivatives Containing a Saturated Thiazole Moiety

Harjit Singh, K. S. Bhandari, and K. S. Narang

Condensation of *N*-allylanthranilic acid hydrochloride with potassium thiocyanate furnishes 1-allyl-2-mercapto-4-keto-tetrahydroquinazoline (V). Cyclisation of (V) with HCl provides 2-methyl-9,10-thiopegan-10-en-4-one (VII). Bromination of (V) results in its cyclisation to 2-bromomethyl-9,10-thiopegan-10-en-4-one, which has been dehydrobrominated to 2-methylene-9,10-thiopegan-10-en-4-one (XI). This compound has been converted by bromination and dehydrobromination to 2-bromomethyl-9,10-thiopegan-2,10-dien-4-one (XIV). The latter has been condensed with piperidine and with morpholine. The products (XI and XIV) on treatment with H₂SO₄, zinc, and acetic acid furnish 2-methyl-9,10-thiopegan-2,10-dien-4-one (XV). The structures of all these compounds have been confirmed by unambiguous synthesis of (XV). Some of these compounds show weak antibacterial activity.

The angular thiopegans (II: R = H or Me; R' = H)¹⁻³ showed antimalarial activity and the linear thiopegans containing reduced thiazole ring (I) exhibited good antibacterial activity⁴⁻⁸. In this communication syntheses of some derivatives of (II) are reported.

(I)

(II)

Trituration of *N*-allylanthranilic acid hydrochloride with potassium thiocyanate and refluxing of the ethanol-soluble product afforded 1-allyl-2-mercapto-4-keto-tetrahydroquinazoline(V). This compound dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and could be recovered on acidification. Moreover, the alkaline solution of compound (V)

1. Khosla *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, 12B, 466.
2. Dhatt and Narang, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 302.
3. Singh and Narang, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 545.
4. Dhami *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, 15B, 690.
5. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1957, 16B, 311.
6. Singh *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1958, 17B, 120.
7. Singh and Sharma, *ibid.*, 1961, 20C, 178.
8. Sachdev *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, 14, 304.

condensed with ω -chloroacetophenone, providing (VI). Both the reactions indicate the presence of

Various reactions pertaining to the experimental part are shown in Chart I. The intermediates (IV), (VIII), and (XII) could not be isolated.

CHART I

CHART I (contd.)
(XI)

That compound (V) on cyclisation furnishes the compounds containing thiazolidine or thiazoline ring (VII, X-XI, XIII-XVII) and not those containing thiazine ring (XVIII) has been confirmed by the following unambiguous synthesis of (XV).

Moreover, this finds an analogy to a previous observation where the isomeric 2-mercapto-3-allyl-4-keto-tetrahydroquinazoline has been shown to cyclise to the system containing a thiazolidine ring rather than the thiazine ring⁸.

On biological screening, compound (X) was found to be effective against *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Shiga*, and *Para dysenteriae* Flexner at a dilution of 1:1000 and compound (XVII) against *S. typhi*, *S. paratyphi*, *S. schottmuelleri*, *Sh. dysenteriae*, *Shiga*, *B. subtilis* and *M. pyogenes, var aureus* at a dilution of 1:5000.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Allylanthranilic Acid Hydrochloride (III).—A solution of *N*-allylanthranilic acid⁹ (20 g.) in dry ether (100 ml) on saturation with dry HCl gas in the cold during 15 min. provided the hydrochloride as a white solid, crystallising from glacial acetic acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 177°, yield 21.5 g. (91%), (Found: N, 6.34; Cl, 16.33. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2NCl$ requires N, 6.55; Cl, 16.63%).

1-Allyl-2-mercapto-4-keto-tetrahydroquinazoline (V).—A mixture of potassium thiocyanate (19.4 g., 0.1M) and the preceding compound (III, 21.4 g., 0.1M) was ground to a thick paste, which solidified within 5 minutes of grinding. Attempts to purify this product were unsuccessful. It was extracted with anhydrous ethanol (4 × 25 ml) and the extract refluxed for 20 hr. After removal of the solvent, the dark viscous residue was poured into a 10% cold sodium carbonate solution (400 ml). The pale yellow product after washing with ethanol (10 ml) weighed 10.4 g. (48%). It was recrystallised from ethanol in pale yellow prisms, m.p. 168°. (Found: C, 60.98; H, 4.41; N, 12.95; S, 14.81. $C_{11}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires C, 60.55; H, 4.58; N, 12.84; S, 15.14%).

1-Allyl-4-keto-tetrahydroquinazolyl-2-mercaptoacetophenone (VI).—A solution of compound (V) (1.1 g., 0.005M) in 2% NaOH (10 ml, 0.005M) was filtered and a solution of ω -chloroacetophenone (0.85 g., 0.005M) in ethanol (6 ml) was added during 5 min. at 36°. The product began to separate at once. It was collected after keeping overnight and crystallised from ethanol in pale needles (0.8 g., 47%), m.p. 197–98°. (Found: C, 67.27; H, 4.32; N, 8.57. $C_{19}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires C, 67.85; H, 4.76; N, 8.33%).

2-Methyl-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-one (VII).—Dry HCl gas was passed through a refluxing solution of (V) (4.0 g.) in glacial acetic acid (60 ml) for 6 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was basified with sodium carbonate solution; it was collected and washed with water. The product was crystallised from dioxane in fine colorless needles (3.2 g., 80%), m.p. 220°. (Found: N, 13.0. $C_{11}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires N, 12.84%).

2-Bromomethyl-9,10-thiopega-10-en-4-one Hydrobromide (IX) and the Free Base (X).—A solution of bromine (0.5 ml, 0.01M) in glacial acetic acid (2 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of (V) (2.2 g., 0.01M) in the same solvent (20 ml) at 70° with constant shaking. Addition of each drop of bromine solution was accompanied by the separation of a solid, which disappeared on shaking. When the addition was complete, the solid persisted. The

*Analyses are by Drs. Weiler & Strauss, Oxford and by Mr. B. N. Anand, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh-3.

9. Houben and Brassert, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3233.

reaction mixture was cooled and the product was collected by filtration. The filtrate on dilution with ether furnished a second crop of the same product; the yield was 2.5 g. (65%). The product was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid in light brown needles, m.p. 360°. (Found: C, 34.66; H, 2.71; N, 7.24; Br, 42.80; S, 8.66. $C_{11}H_{10}ON_2Br_2S$ requires C, 34.9; H, 2.6; N, 7.41; Br, 43.14; S, 8.46%).

A 1% NaOH solution (40 ml, 0.01M) was added to a solution of the above hydrobromide (3.8 g., 0.01M) in 60% ethanol (60 ml) at 40°. The product obtained on cooling was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in white rectangular plates, m.p. 180°, yield 2.5 g. (82%). (Found: N, 9.39. $C_{11}H_9ON_2BrS$ requires N, 9.43%).

2-Methylene-9,10-thiopega-10-en-4-one (XI).—(a). A 2% NaOH solution (20 ml, 0.01 M) was added to a solution of the hydrobromide (IX) (1.9 g., 0.005M) in 70% ethanol (40 ml) at 45°. On chilling in an ice-salt mixture, a white product was obtained which was collected by filtration. The filtrate on further dilution with water and cooling deposited a second crop of the same product; the combined yield was 0.8 g. (74%). Crystallisation from dilute ethanol provided white flakes, m.p. 264°.

(b). A solution of piperidine (2.55 g., 0.03M) and the hydrobromide (IX) (3.8 g., 0.01M) in anhydrous ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. After removing the solvent, the residue was washed with water and collected (1.1 g., 66%). The substance was crystallised from ethanol as white flakes, m.p. 264°. The melting point was not depressed on admixture with the product from (a).

(c). A solution of the base (X) (1.5 g., 0.005M) in dioxane (25 ml) was mixed with a 3% EtOH-KOH solution (10 ml, 0.005M) and the resulting solution was refluxed for 6 hr. After removal of the solvent and isolation of the product as under (a) and (b), a total yield of 0.6 g. (70%) was obtained. (Found: N, 12.73. $C_{11}H_9ON_2S$ requires N, 12.96%).

2-Bromomethyl-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-one Hydrobromide (XIII) and its Free Base (XIV).—Bromine (1.6 g., 0.01M), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2.0 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of the methylene base (XI) (2.2 g., 0.01M) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) at 40° with continuous shaking of the reaction mixture. A crystalline solid separated instantaneously. It was cooled and collected by filtration. The filtrate on dilution with dry ether deposited a second crop of the same product; the combined yield was 2.8 g. (73%). It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in light brown needles, m.p. 335°. (Found: N, 7.56; S, 8.58. $C_{11}H_9ON_2Br_2S$ requires N, 7.42; S, 9.08%).

The above hydrobromide on stirring with sodium carbonate solution afforded a brown product which was collected and washed with water; the yield was 1.1 g. (88%). Crystallisation from ethanol furnished light brown rectangular plates, m.p. 230°. (Found: N, 9.71. $C_{11}H_7ON_2BrS$ requires N, 9.49%).

2-Methyl-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-one (XV). (a). *Isomerisation of* (XI).—The methylene base (1 g.) was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (conc., 15 ml) at 10°. After about 5 min. it was poured on crushed ice. A white solid separating was collected after 10 minutes and washed with water. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol in colorless, elongated needles (0.5 g., 50%), m.p. 206°.

(b). *Reductive Debromination of (XIV)*.—Zinc dust (10 g.) was added slowly to a gently boiling solution of the bromo-base (XIV, 1.2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) during 30 min. The mixture was gently boiled for 15 min. more and was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to about one-third of its volume and was diluted with water (30 ml). The flocculent precipitate was collected. On crystallisation from dilute ethanol, it furnished the same product (0.3 g., 34%) as in (a), on the basis of a mixed m.p. determination. (Found: N, 13.23. $C_{11}H_9ON_2S$ requires N, 12.96%).

2-Piperidinomethyl-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-one (XVI).—Piperidine (2.55 g., 0.03M) was added to a suspension of the hydrobromide (XIII) (3.8 g., 0.01M) in anhydrous ethanol (75ml) and the mixture was heated for 8 hr. A clear solution was obtained within a few minutes of refluxing. After removal of the solvent, the residue was washed with water; the yield was 2.0 g. (87%). It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless flakes, m.p. 220°. (Found: C, 64.19; H, 5.57. $C_{16}H_{17}ON_2S$ requires C, 64.21; H, 5.78%).

2-Morpholinomethyl-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-one (XVII).—The hydrobromide (XIII) (3.8 g., 0.01M) and morpholine (2.61 g., 0.03M) were condensed as above. The product was crystallised from dilute ethanol in light brown flakes, m.p. 160°, yield 1.8 g. (60%). (Found: N, 14.43, 14.15. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 13.95%).

N-β-Chloroallylanthranilic Acid (XIX).—To anthranilic acid (6.65 g.), dissolved in an aqueous solution of potassium carbonate (6.9 g.), β-chloroallyl chloride (6 g.) and potassium iodide (2 g.) were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 9-10 hr. It was cooled and acidified with a drop of acetic acid. The solid separating was collected and crystallised from dilute ethanol in light brown needles, m.p. 124-25°. (Found; N, 7.11. $C_{10}H_9O_2NCl$ requires N, 6.63%).

1-β-Chloroallyl-2-thio-4-keto-tetrahydroquinazoline (XX).—*N-β-Chloroallylanthranilic acid* (5.2 g.) and KSCN (2.6 g.) were ground together with 2-3 ml of HCl. The reaction mixture was taken in ethanol (60 ml) and refluxed for about 20 hr. After removal of the solvent, the residue was treated with an aqueous sodium carbonate solution and crystallised from dilute ethanol as a white mass, m.p. 189-92°. (Found: N, 10.8. $C_{11}H_9ON_2ClS$ requires N, 11.07%).

2-Methyl-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-one (XV).—Dry HCl gas was passed through a boiling solution of compound (XX) in anhydrous ethanol for about 8 hr. After removal of the solvent and basification of the residue with aqueous NaOH solution, the residue was crystallised from ethanol in colorless, elongated needles, m.p. 206°. It did not depress the m.p. of the sample obtained in previous experiments on admixture.